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Survey on the European University alliance E³UDRES²

The university alliance E³UDRES², is asking the population what they know about the Alliance and which topics are relevant for innovation and sustainability in regions.

Universities for innovation and sustainability in rural regions

In 2020, the European high-level alliance E³UDRES²: Engaged - European - Entrepreneurial University as Driver for European Smart and Sustainable Regions was launched. It is dedicated to the role of universities in innovation and sustainability in rural regions and wants to support medium-sized cities and their rural environments on the way to becoming “smart and sustainable regions”.

Nine universities from all over Europe are currently involved. Over 100,000 students benefit from the diverse activities and the numerous opportunities for mobility and intercultural exchange of experiences.

“One of the objectives of the Ent-r-e-novators project is to co-create a common strategy and agenda that unlocks the potential of the E³UDRES² European University alliance for excellence in Research and Innovation, to accelerate the transformation into a multi-institutional European Research and Innovation Centre for Smart and Sustainable Regions. To achieve this objective, it is necessary for E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators to include, interact and collaborate with a diverse variety of smart and ambitious people, academic institutions, regional authorities, companies, European R&I networks and regional innovation ecosystems. It is for this reason that the Ent-r-e-novators project developed and is distributing this survey, hoping that the respective target group recognizes the importance of the project and specifically this survey and collaborates in responding to it”, says Luís Coelho from Polytechnic of Setúbal, lead coordinator of the project.

Survey: exchange with population

E³UDRES² is currently conducting a survey during this month. The survey asks whether people have ever heard of the alliance, how well they know it and whether they have ever taken part in any of the projects and

activities. The target group is students, those interested in research and universities, and the public. We count on your participation <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/ENTRN-WP2-Survey2>.

The survey also determines whether the topics that E³UDRES² deals with are relevant for the respondents and their region and whether there are specific challenges in the regions that E³UDRES² could help with.

“With the survey, we are strengthening an essential aspect of our university of applied sciences and our European university alliance: being open universities for the regions, involving people in research and innovation and exchanging ideas with the population as a university and university alliance,” says Gabi Permoser, head of the FH -Services for research and knowledge transfer at the St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences.

Project Ent-r-e-novators

The survey is carried out as part of the “E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators” project. The aim is to develop the strategic framework conditions for further intensive cooperation in research and innovation within the E³UDRES² alliance.

The E³UDRES² alliance is particularly concerned with developing the potential of researchers, teachers, but also learners and guiding them to become “Ent-r-e-novators” (i.e. entrepreneurs, researchers, teachers, innovators *in).

"Ent-r-e-novators connect entrepreneurs, researchers, teachers and innovators, so they are solution-oriented, curious and open-minded people who assume their social and societal responsibility and take the interests of the general public into account. They take a leading role in innovation of educational and research institutions and in their transformation towards open and integrative ecosystems. Inclusion and interdisciplinarity are the main pillars of the project," says Hannes Raffaseder, Managing Director of the St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences and coordinator of E³UDRES² Alliance.

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